

DeepCardioPlanner: Deep Learning-based tool for automatic CMR planning

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Synopsis

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Cardiac Magnetic Resonance (CMR) is a powerful technique which can be used to perform a comprehensive cardiac examination. However, its adoption is often limited to specialised centres, in part due to the need for highly trained operators to perform the complex procedures of determining the 4 standard cardiac planes: 2-, 3-, 4-chamber and short axis views. To automate view planning, a deep learning-based tool (DeepCardioPlanner) has been proposed to regress the view defining vectors from a rapidly acquired 3D image. It successfully takes advantage of multi-objective learning to allow accurate, fast and reproducible view prescriptions without any operator input.

Introduction

Cardiac Magnetic Resonance (CMR) provides a comprehensive cardiac examination, namely by assessing ventricular function, cardiac morphology, vasculature, perfusion, viability, and metabolism.

However, CMR requires highly trained operators for determining the standard double-oblique view planes: short axis (SAX), 2-chamber (2CH), 3-chamber (3CH), and 4-chamber (4CH) views. These patient-specific planes are traditionally prescribed through a multistep planning process, requiring several scout scans and manual adjustments, which increase the scan time and workflow complexity.

Tools for automating this planning process have been proposed (e.g., Cardiac Dot¹), but still require some user input. Recently, Deep Learning (DL) methods have been proposed to achieve automatic cardiac planning^{2,3,4,5}. For example, cardiac anatomic landmark regression from 2D images has been used to prescribe the standard CMR view planes with good results^{2,4}, but it requires extensive manual annotation to build a dataset to train such methods. Manual annotation free methods have also been proposed for computed tomography (CT), but predict each view position and orientation separately³. A similar approach based on rapidly acquired volumetric images could be applicable to CMR where automated view planning would be even more valuable.

Here, we propose a set of four deep convolutional neural network (CNN) models (DeepCardioPlanner), each trained via a multi-task learning approach, to predict the orientation and position of each cardiac view plane from a rapidly acquired 3D scan. We tested the ability of DeepCardioPlanner to automatically plan the four cardiac views on clinically acquired patient CMR data.

Methods

Dataset: The dataset consists of 120 3D CMR (51% with, 49% without contrast) patient scans labelled with the defining vectors of each of the 4 standard CMR view planes (Fig.1c). The datasets were obtained from patients with different pathologies and by different operators. Data was acquired on a 1.5T Philips scanner, using standard clinical protocols and an ECG-triggered volumetric bSSFP sequence with field-of-view=440x440x150 mm³, voxel size=3x3x3mm³, compressed SENSE acceleration factor six, and scan time of 10 seconds (assuming 60 bpm heart rate).

Pre-processing: Image intensity was standardised, and the 3D images were resized to 95x95x42 with a 4mm isotropic resolution to reduce computational burden.

Training: To address the plane position and orientation subtasks simultaneously, training was performed by combining two losses. Leveraging knowledge that a plane is defined by a point within it and a normal vector, the plane position loss is set to the Euclidean distance between a predicted point and the plane, and the orientation loss is computed as the cosine similarity between the predicted and ground truth normal vectors. The multi-objective loss used to train the network was the combination of these two losses via an uncertainty based trainable loss weighting approach⁶.

Regularisation is ensured by weight decay and early stopping. Data augmentation (e.g., additive noise, scaling, translation, rotation) is also used to increase the models' generalisability.

A stratified 74-13-13 training-validation-test split was used with Adam⁷ optimizer. Learning rate and augmentation hyperparameters were tuned separately for each view model through a grid search approach.

Network Architectures: Two different architectures were compared for the final DeepCardioPlanner tool. Architecture A (N_A), similar to Chen et al³, consists of a feature extraction block with five stages of two 3D convolutional layers connected through a batch normalisation operation and followed by a final max pooling layer. The final regression block is used to regress the two vectors that define the given plane (Fig.2a). Architecture B (N_B) is the same but with separate regression heads for each subtask (Fig.2b).

Performance Metrics: Performance on the position prediction subtask is assessed by the displacement error (ϵ_d), which is the same as position loss, and the orientation subtask is assessed through the angulation error (ϵ_θ), which is the angle between predicted and ground truth plane normal vectors.

Results

DeepCardioPlanner takes <1sec to prescribe a given view. Even though ϵ_d and ϵ_θ may appear large, they do not always correspond to a great loss of image plane quality from visual assessment (Fig.3&4).

N_B yields a better performance in both subtasks for the 2CH view than N_A . Sharing parameters from all the layers was constraining the learning process (Fig.3). Hence, the architecture chosen to train all view models was N_B .

After hyperparameter tuning for each specific view dataset, a model for each view was obtained. Performance metrics are within the literature ranges for the same task with CT and wherein plane orientation and position are predicted separately. Also, DeepCardioPlanner yields test errors at the scale of the inter-operator variability³ (Fig.5).

Conclusion

The proposed DeepCardioPlanner tool successfully takes advantage of multi-objective learning to provide good and fast view prescriptions for all four standard CMR view planes. This automatic method has the potential to greatly reduce examination time and complexity as it is based on 10sec scans and ~1sec prescription time, which may increase efficiency and clinical utility of CMR. Furthermore, DeepCardioPlanner improves upon previous methods by doing this without requiring manually annotated datasets and only needing one model per view. Results can potentially be enhanced through a larger training set with a more refined multi-objective learning approach.

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Figures

Figure 1 - a) Input volume for a representative subject, b) 2D mid slices (coronal, sagittal and transverse) and c) corresponding ground truth standard view planes and their view defining vectors: \vec{o}_1 and \vec{o}_2 define orientation and \vec{t} defines the location of the plane's centre. Includes a scheme of each image plane position and orientation within the volume.

Figure 2 - Structure of the two main CNN architectures tested. a) Fully shared architecture (N_A) between position and orientation tasks. b) Partially shared architecture (N_B) with two different fully connected blocks for separate prediction of position and orientation vectors. In both schemes, \vec{n} is the plane's normal vector orthogonal to \vec{o}_1 and \vec{o}_2 , and \vec{t} is the position of a point within the target plane (see Fig.1).

Figure 3 - a) Box plot of the test set position and orientation performance of two 2CH models, one trained on a fully shared architecture (N_A) and the other on a partially shared one (N_B). Median values indicated by an orange dash and the mean values by a green triangle. b) Ground truth and predicted 2CH slices by each of the models. Median angulation error at test sample P018 in both models. Median position error at sample P006 for N_A and at sample P013 for N_B .

Figure 3 - a) Box plot of the displacement and angulation error on the test set from best view models trained on a partially shared architecture (N_B ; DeepCardioPlanner) for each view's dataset. Median values indicated by an orange dash and the mean values by a green triangle. b) Ground truth and predicted slices by the best model tuned for each view. The two samples shown for each view correspond to median orientation performance (top) and median position performance (bottom).

Figure 5 - Comparison of test performances between our proposed method and the method by Chen et al³. DeepCardioPlanner: Our performances; where DL-reader1: Their performances on samples from the same operator that generated their training set; DL-reader2: Their performances on samples from a never seen operator; Inter-reader: Differences in plane location and orientation between the two operators.